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European Academic Science and Research

ACADEMIC EDITION

ISSN 2789-1968

Online ISSN 2789-195X

Proceedings
of the **scholarly abstracts**
European Academic
Science and Research

May,
2022

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**INVESTMENT CLIMATE ANALYSIS USING THE RISK ASSESSMENT
METHODOLOGY: FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT IN JORDAN**

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Key words: FDI, Investment Risk, Euromny, Jordan.

Jordan is a developing country that suffers from many economic structural imbalances, the most important of which is the lack of funding needed to implement many development and economic projects and solve the problem of unemployment. The study aims to assess the Jordanian investment climate and the extent of the Jordanian economy's ability to attract foreign direct investment in the period spanning 2000 to 2018. The paper used the descriptive approach and the investment risk analysis tool. The investment risk analysis tools used in the study are the composite index of economic policies, the global competitiveness index, the Euromoney index of investment risks, the human development index, and finally the index of restricting foreign direct investment legislation. The various results of the analysis showed that Jordan is considered one of the countries with medium investment risks. This study is considered one of the rare studies evaluating the Jordanian investment climate and provided some recommendations to decision-makers in order to improve the classification of Jordan within the investment risk indicators.

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TREATMENT OF CONTAMINATED WATER UNDER THE INFLUENCE OF NEW SURFACTANT BASED ON (Z)-OCTADEC-9-ENOIC ACID AND 1,2-DIAMINOETHANE.

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In the last hundred years which might well be called the age of oil, the escape of oil into the environment has increased gradually in quantity and has become recently more objectionable causing oil pollution.

Pollution of water basins with crude oil and oil products is one of the principal problems facing mankind currently. Due to various reasons, including accidents in oil tankers and oil pipelines, a huge amount of crude oil enters the hydrosphere. After removing thick oil films by mechanical means on the water surface there always remains a thin oil film which is ecologically hazardous as it seriously disorders gas (mainly oxygen and carbon dioxide) and energy (sunlight) exchange at the water-air interface, thereby negatively impacting life conditions of hydrobionts. Such thin films may be liquidated only using colloid-chemical

methods that include an application of petroleum-collecting and petroleum dispersing reagents [1-5].

So in this research work, it was planned to synthesize and study new and efficient reagents possessing petroleum-collecting and petroleum-dispersing capabilities. These chemicals are considered to be obtained based on (Z)-octadec-9-enoic acid and nitrogen-containing compound. (Z)-octadec-9-enoic acid (0.01mol) was taken at an equimolar ratio with 1,2-diaminoethane. The components of reactions were mixed, closed well, and placed in a thermostat at a temperature ranging between 50 and 60°C for a period ranging between 15 and 20 hours. The obtained complex is generally viscous liquid and solid. Their colors vary from light yellow to dark brown. The synthesis of the complexes can be illustrated by the following reaction scheme:

The structure of the synthesized complex was confirmed by FTIR, C^{13} , and H^1 -NMR spectra. The studied physicochemical indices are solubility in different solvents (water, ethyl alcohol, CCl_4 , toluene, and kerosene), electro-conductivity, and amine number. From measurement, it is noted that the obtained complex is generally viscous liquid and solid. Their colors vary from yellow to blackish-brown color. Measurements of the electrical conductivity of different concentrations of aqueous solutions of the complex indicate their polarity. Determination of the amine number for this complex was done (5.1 mg HCl/g). Such a selection is stipulated by the fact that previously in the above-indicated laboratory, surface-active compounds with a hydrocarboxyl group ensure a sufficient hydrophobicity, when having nitrogen-containing fragments in the hydrophilic part, possess strong petro-collecting and petro-dispersing properties.

Surface-active properties (interfacial tension) of the salt of dodecanoic acid with 1,2 aminoethane was determined using a tensiometer at the air-water interface using their aqueous solutions at various concentrations in the range of 0.01%-0.5%, at room temperature (25°C). It has been established that this complex ($\sigma=21.09$ mN/m) at concentrations (0.3%) exhibits high surface activity. The surface tension of distilled water at the border with air is 72.82 ± 0.2 mN/m without surfactant.

Surface properties studied included critical micelle concentration (CMC), maximum surface excess (Γ_{max}), Efficiency (pC_{30}), and minimum surface area (A_{min}). Free energies of micellization (ΔG_{mic}^0) and adsorption (ΔG_{ads}^0) were calculated.

The synthesized complex has very good surface-active properties and may be used as petroleum-collecting and petroleum-dispersing agents for removing thin petroleum films from water surfaces as well as a corrosion inhibitor and antimicrobial agent.

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DEVELOPMENT OF A SENSOR FOR MONITORING THE CONCENTRATION OF VIRUSES IN ENVIRONMENT

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The development of a **sensor for monitoring the concentration of viruses** in environment is currently focused on pathogenic viruses, and researchers are ready to use these approaches to detect viral infections. Indeed, during pandemics, innovative structures based on nanotechnology and nano biotechnology can be used for rapid, sensitive and reliable detection of pathogenic viruses to control and prevent and reduce their spread, which is important in the case of a COVID-19 pandemic.

As a rule, the currently used COVID-19 **detection method** is a real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction technology, but it is time-consuming and cannot be used promptly in remote or limited resources. This may lead to obstacles in obtaining factual data on the infectious and transmission of SARS-CoV-2.

There are two most common types of COVID-19 tests on the market. The first uses polymerase chain reaction (PCR) and nucleic acid hybridization strategies to identify viral RNA. Diagnostic tests approved by the FDA use this method. However, they have a major drawback: the time required to perform the test, as well as the need for specialized personnel and mandatory access to equipment and reagents.

The second category of tests is focused on the **detection** of antibodies. However, it may take from several days to several weeks after a person has been exposed to the virus to develop antibodies.

In recent years, researchers have made some progress in creating **biosensors** that are used in medical care centers. To create them, the developers used two-dimensional nanomaterials, for example, graphene. It is needed to detect diseases. The main advantages of graphene-based biosensors are their sensitivity, as well as low production costs and fast results.

The biosensor consists of two components: a platform for measuring electrical parameters and probes that detect viral RNA. To create the platform, the researchers first coated the filter paper with a layer of graphene nano plates to create a conductive film. They then placed a gold electrode on top of graphene as a contact pad for electrical reading. Both gold and graphene have high sensitivity and conductivity, which makes this platform super-sensitive: it can detect changes in electrical signals.

Due to the possibility of such pandemics in the future and in order to control and prevent the further spread of viral diseases, there is an urgent and vital need to develop fast, sensitive and inexpensive methods for **detecting viruses** and diagnosing related viral infections.

The sensor can help provide rapid and sensitive detection of SARS-CoV-2 virus particles, helping to better monitor, diagnose and treat COVID-19.

One of the important tasks in creating suitable sensors is to capture a signal of very low magnitude that occurs between biological species (bioreceptor and the analyzed substance).

However, limited analyses have been carried out to develop these nanomaterial-based biosensors for the detection of SARS. Nano and biosensors should be technically developed for highly effective detection of SARS-CoV-2 in various clinical samples, including urine, blood, saliva and nasopharyngeal swabs.

The detection limit is very important because of the relatively low concentration of the virus in patient samples; it seems that magnetic, plasma and electrochemical devices showed the lowest LOD, indicating that they are promising methods. However, an important disadvantage of these magnetic and plasma methods is that they usually require special equipment for both production and operation, which creates complex problems with portability. Therefore, improved procedures are urgently needed to make them more portable, as well as to increase their sensitivity for use in POCKET. In addition, some methods based on colorimetric, electrochemical and lateral flow analyses have demonstrated greater portability, allowing them to work better in the field, since they do not require laboratory infrastructure and instruments to obtain results.

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**ANALYSIS OF THE INNOVATION POLICY OF THE REPUBLIC OF
KAZAKHSTAN**

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Keywords: analysis, innovation, program, public administration, laws, development, financing

О необходимости перехода Республики Казахстан к инновационному экономическому развитию на государственном уровне впервые заговорили на заседании Правительства РК 8 июля 2004 года, когда рассматривался вопрос о формировании национальной инновационной системы, подготовленный Министерством индустрии и торговли. Этот стратегически важный документ, утвержденный на самом высоком уровне, впервые определил задачи Казахстана в области научно-технологической политики и инноваций [1].

В дальнейшем в результате системных многолетних усилий со стороны государства инновации были определены как стратегически важное направление развития РК.

Глава государства в Послании народу Казахстана от 10 января 2018 года «новые возможности развития в условиях Четвертой промышленной революции» отметил, что вступление мира в четвертую промышленную революцию требует готовности к глобальным изменениям и требованиям новой эпохи. Казахстану требуется новое качество развития. Глобальные тренды предполагают реализацию на основе широкого внедрения элементов Четвертой промышленной революции [2].

Единственной правильной моделью экономического роста Казахстана является инновационная модель развития. Инновационный путь развития экономики, основанный на многогранных технологических, экономических, организационных и социальных нововведениях, предъявляет свои новые требования.

На сегодняшний день инновационное развитие является одним из основных путей экономического роста, обеспечивающих конкурентоспособность страны.

Основной целью государственной инновационной политики было формирование сбалансированного сектора исследований и разработок и эффективной инновационной системы, обеспечивающей технологическую модернизацию экономики и повышение ее конкурентоспособности на основе передовых технологий, и превращение научного потенциала в один из основных ресурсов устойчивого экономического роста [3].

Результаты основных инновационных программ, принятых в Казахстане, представлены в таблице 1.

Таблица 1-перечень программ Республики Казахстан по развитию инноваций

№	Наименование программы развития инноваций
1	Стратегия индустриально-инновационного развития Республики Казахстан на 2003-2015 годы
2	Государственная программа развития образования и науки Республики Казахстан на 2005-2010 годы
3	Программа по формированию и развитию национальной инновационной системы Республики Казахстан на 2005-2015 годы
4	Программа технологического развития Республики Казахстан до 2015 года №1131 от 26.11.2007 г.
5	Концепция достижения качественно нового уровня конкурентоспособности и экспортных возможностей экономики Республики Казахстан от 28 декабря 2007 года № 1332 на 2008-2015 годы
6	Государственная программа развития "электронного правительства" на 2008-2010 годы
7	Государственная программа форсированного индустриально-инновационного развития на 2010-2014 годы
8	Государственная программа индустриально-инновационного развития на 2015-2019 годы
9	Государственная программа развития образования и науки Республики Казахстан на 2016-2019 годы
10	Государственная программа "Цифровой Казахстан"
11	Государственная программа индустриально-инновационного развития на 2020-2025 годы

Таким образом, инновации и развитие наукоемких производств на протяжении более десяти лет остаются стратегическим приоритетом Республики Казахстан. Несмотря на это, в Казахстане очень медленно развиваются инновации и наукоемкие производства.

Так, в Казахстане в 2021 году доля произведенной инновационной продукции по отношению к ВВП составила 1,6 % ВВП, при этом в 2005 году этот показатель был равен 0,92% [4].

Таблица 2 – Доля инновационной продукции (товаров, услуг) в ВВП Республики Казахстан, %

Показатель	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Доля инновационной продукции (товаров, услуг) в ВВП, %	0,92	0,95	1,55	1,72	1,60	2,43	1,60

Разработка и вывод на рынок инноваций, освоение новых рынков, повышение эффективности или улучшение качества предполагают инвестиции в исследовательскую инфраструктуру и человеческий капитал.

Тенденция огромного технологического отставания Республики Казахстан от стран-лидеров вызвана сильной зависимостью экономики от добывающих отраслей. В связи с ресурсозависимостью казахстанской экономики наблюдается недостаточное инвестирование инновационных разработок, способных существенно снизить этот разрыв.

Отечественная продукция всех перспективных направлений неконкурентоспособна на фоне аналогичных товаров, производимых в Китае, США, Германии, Японии и даже странах СНГ. Предприятия в сфере высокотехнологичной продукции Казахстана не могут удовлетворить спрос внутри страны и, как следствие, выйти на зарубежные рынки.

Общеизвестно, что рост современной экономики основан на эффективном инновационном развитии. Инновации являются важной предпосылкой технологических и структурных изменений, которые способствуют росту и конкурентоспособности. На уровне компании инновации являются разновидностью продуктов высокого риска.

Эффективность нововведения во многом зависит от механизма финансовой поддержки. Финансирование инноваций в соответствии с действующим законодательством осуществляется за счет собственных средств субъектов инновационной деятельности, средств республиканского и местных бюджетов, средств инновационных фондов, государственных натуральных грантов, а также иных источников в соответствии с законодательством Республики Казахстан.

В последние годы в стране наблюдается устойчивый тренд роста производства инновационной продукции. Для активизации инновационной деятельности страна должна увеличить объем средств на развитие научных исследований [5].

Анализ зарубежного опыта показывает, что Национальная инновационная система будет эффективной, если в стране будет развитый предпринимательский сектор, характеризующийся низким уровнем инновационной активности в Казахстане.

Рассматривая собственные средства субъектов инновационной деятельности, следует отметить, что в современных условиях в Казахстане они мало заинтересованы в развитии инноваций либо отсутствуют достаточные объемы финансовых ресурсов для их продвижения. В целом, на сегодняшний день большая часть инновационной деятельности в Казахстане непосредственно стимулируется государством, и большая часть научно-исследовательских работ проводится в государственных лабораториях.

Доступ к финансовым ресурсам является одной из ключевых проблем в вопросах эффективного инновационного развития. В целом количество технически реализуемых и востребованных инновационных идей в фирмах превышает их возможности финансирования с помощью имеющихся ресурсов. Ограниченные финансовые возможности тем самым снижают инновационную активность фирм [6].

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**FORMATION OF THE POLYLINGUAL PERSONALITY OF FUTURE OFFICERS
IN THE CONDITIONS OF MILITARY EDUCATION SYSTEM**

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The state educational policy in the field of learning of foreign languages is based on recognition of importance of all languages and creations of necessary conditions for multilingualism development in the territory Republic of Kazakhstan. Along with Russian and Kazakh languages, communication is carried out more than in hundred languages, including languages of ethnic minorities. These circumstances create a reliable basis for development of multilingualism of the individual and for creation of relevance of studying not only languages of the people of the ethnic groups living near it, but also international languages. Multilingualism, being the most important factor of spiritual life of the modern polycultural world, intensifies political and economical contacts, at the same time increasing the pragmatism importance of foreign language skills. Foreign languages are the center defining language policy of the country, having social and economical specifics, the priority international relations, educational opportunities, needs for personnel for whom this or that foreign language can be priority.

At all times knowledge of a foreign language was considered as a sign of culture, education. According to many experts to master the native language in full degree – that is to estimate all its opportunities - it is possible, only studying any foreign language.

The polycultural society at a boundary of a new millennium represents such educational space in which pupils of different ethnolinguistic religious and socioeconomic accessory live and are trained. Therefore, military education, being a component of the general national education in Kazakhstan as it is demanded by time, has to be polylingual. Future officer, being a full-fledged representative of our society has to know languages. At military institute, one of important tasks is familiarizing of younger generation with universal, global values, formation at abilities to communicate to interact with representatives of various next cultures and in world space.

Thus, problems of polylingual education at Military educational institute can become:

- formation at cadets of ideas of multilingualism;
- education of the tolerant relation to language and cultural distinctions, overcoming of negative ethnosocial stereotypes;
- formation of language skills with carriers of various cultures;
- formation at cadets the culture of international communication.

The polycultural identity of future officer is an individual with the developed linguistic consciousness. Language is base of formation of the person of the informative and sociocultural person of a new era. After all language and communication – the main condition of existence of the person in community with other people. There is a competent question - how many languages future officer needs to know? Obvious not less than three and one of them foreign – as means of common cultural development.

The knowledge of culture of the Kazakh people of dialogue of cultures of the foreign-language countries can become culturological aspect in training in a foreign language in the system of military education, after all understanding of native national culture is especially

brightly shown by its comparison to cultures of other people. Dialogue of cultures in teaching of a foreign language opens variety and unity of the world before pupils, helps to understand the values of different people. All this will teach to live and communicate in multinational Kazakhstan. As the purpose of training the development in future officer the ability to cross-cultural interaction where the foreign language is used as an instrument of this interaction has to serve any foreign language in Military institutes. How the tasks of the polycultural personality directly at lessons of a foreign language are carried out? The solution of polycultural education demands the use of active methods of training and education a leading place in which takes creative and search activity of cadets, discussions, group and individual work, role-playing games, project works during which the cadets gains experience in the solution of problems. Exactly here, the trainee acts as the creator – the main character. Formation of the polycultural personality on classes in a foreign language promotes the use of interactive methods of the training developing ability and skills of a speaking. As example are the lessons on which there is an acquaintance with culture of studied language countries, with features the creativity of various writers, etc.

Each teacher knows what huge potential out-of-class and educational work possesses. In days of carrying out the Week of the languages, dated to celebration the Day of languages of Kazakhstan people the competitions on knowledge the customs traditions of the people occupying Kazakhstan, and also foreign countries are organized. Belonging to this or that nationality, the ability to express it by means of a foreign language created the atmosphere of a holiday, fun, in which all participants participate to action on a scene and desire to participate in this action. Participation in this action of cadets, representatives of Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan was the culmination moment.

Holiday “Nauryz”, out-of-class activities “Holidays and national traditions of Europe”, “St. Valentine's Day”, “Halloween” and others allow cadets to put knowledge of a foreign language into practice, promote development of the principle of the interconnected training in language and cultures of studied language.

Use in work of a method of the project allows turning the lesson of foreign language into debatable research club in which problems taking into account features of culture of the country are solved. Project “I am proud of my Homeland”, “English-speaking countries”, “Education system in America and Kazakhstan”, “Armed Forces of Kazakhstan and other countries”, “We are in the heart of Eurasia”. “Military conflicts”, etc. The great interest causes carrying out polylingual games and KVN, other lessons with application of elements of integration (travelling lessons, a teleconference “Germany, Great Britain, Kazakhstan”, “Military conflicts all over the world”). At the department of foreign languages there was a tradition to carry out competitions of oratorical skill, the simultaneous interpreter in English, Kazakh and Russian languages.

Planning similar lessons, a main objective is not the simple acquaintance with this or that material, and aspiration to realize the main direction of polylingual education - perception of language as means of cross-cultural interaction. The offered forms of carrying out the lessons in the system of Military education will give the chance to involve all cadets in active oral practice in all languages, in particular in the state Kazakh language, German, Russian and English languages. The communicative technique has to be put in a basis of lesson, is integrated with traditional elements of teaching.

Based on the carried-out analysis, there is a belief that the multilingual environment in Kazakhstan, joint activity of numerous nationalities living by a row and the nations create ideal conditions for formation natural polylinguals, other languages spiritually rich and prepared for perception and cultures. The multilingualism promotes formation of the open

person – open for the world, people, good and ready to activity for the benefit of other people what has to be the real officer.

Polylingual military education an important component of the modern general education promoting assimilation by pupils of knowledge of other languages, cultural values of the people and traditions, a way of life, youth education in the spirit of respect of foreign-language vital world outlook values. Polylingual education, being the best means for knowledge of the native language, serves the development of dialectic thinking, outlook expansion, and formation of future officer.

ACADEMIC EDITION

Proceedings
of the **scholarly abstracts**
European Academic
Science and Research

31 May, 2022

Publisher:
“EASR”
SciPub.de